

A BRIEF REVIEW ON HERBAL HAIR GEL- IT" S FORMULATION AND EVALUATION PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

Herbal hair gels are synthetic free products that promote hair health. It promotes nourishment to the scalp, moisturizes hair, reduces hair fall, regulates growth, and addresses scalp issues like dandruff. Herbal gels enhance growth of hair and are suitable for various hair types. Additionally, they focus on using environmentally sustainable, biodegradable ingredients. The formulation was evaluated for pH, viscosity, spread ability, washability, stability studies, and microbial load, all of which met acceptable cosmetic standards. The results indicate that the herbal hair gel offers effective styling properties along with added therapeutic benefits, making it a promising and safe alternative to conventional chemical-based hair gels. This review includes some herbal drugs used to formulate the hair gel for its excellent hair nourishing and conditioning activity. In nature various herbs are there which can activate hair growth and effectively decrease certain scalp infections. As by choosing suitable gelling agents the herbal drugs can be formulated and evaluated for its consistency, Viscosity, pH, spreadibility and zone of inhibition.

KEYWORD: Spreadibility, Viscosity, Herbal drugs, Zone of inhibition.

INTRODUCTION

A gel is a semi-solid system in which a liquid phase is trapped within a matrix of colloidal particles or polymers that are cross-linked in three dimensions. Gels have qualities that make them both solid and liquid, which makes them useful in a number of disciplines, including materials science, food, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals.^{[2][7][8][10]}

Herbal hair gels are gentler and safer for the skin, non-greasy, hypoallergenic, non-toxic, less prone to irritation and pore clogging, stable gelling agents that mix well and won't interact with active ingredients also, swelling property is essential for entrapment of drug.

Herbal cosmetics unlike Chemical cosmetics, do not interfere with endocrine balance and do not produce negative skin reactions hence are in demand.^{[3][5]}

Alopecia is an autoimmune skin condition characterized by partial or total hair loss on the scalp or body, occurring in individuals of any age. Though not life-threatening, it results in considerable psychological and social distress, particularly in females, resulting in anxiety, depression, and poor self-esteem.^[4]

Healthy, strong, and beautiful hair starts with proper care that nourishes the scalp, prevents damage, and boosts confidence. Hair care routines protect against heat, chemicals, pollution, and poor handling—key causes of breakage, dryness, and dullness.^[5]

Advantages of using herbal ingredients are: aloe vera-moisturizes, neem-cleanses, amla-gives shine, hibiscus-conditions, fenugreek-fortifies roots, and flaxseed-adds smoothness. Curry leaves-stimulate growth, calm the scalp, and add color intensity, Hibiscus rosa- sinensis has

the ability to promote hair development and is suggested as a herbal remedy for a variety of illnesses.^{[5][6]}

Oils, creams, ointments, pastes, and gels are types of topical formulations, Gels are increasingly popular these days because of their superior stability and capacity to provide controlled release when compared to other semisolid preparations.

Traditionally, several plants and their products and extract have been used in hair gel preparation (as herbs or spices) as a mode of hair growth agent as well as a cure for some of the common ailments afflicting humans reduces dandruff and to combat alopecia.^[7]

Herbal cosmetics are produced from naturally available, plant-derived ingredients without synthetic or dangerous chemicals like alcohols and silicones.

Multiple plant extracts combine to form a polyherbal hair gel, the gel's overall effectiveness in treating common hair issues like dryness, psoriasis, dandruff, and hair loss is improved by the synergistic action of specific herbs it also proves to have fewer side effects. An efficient and all-natural substitute for synthetic hair care products, these natural substances aid in restoring the moisture balance of the hair, preserving the pH of the scalp, controlling sebum production, and promoting healthy hair development.^[11]

Ayurvedic formulations are being improved using cutting-edge methods like extraction, mechanical processing, and software-based optimization.^[14]

Dandruff is a skin disorder that causes the scalp to flake and can become slightly itchy. Numerous bacteria and fungi can cause scalp infections, which can then result in additional skin or hair problems.

As topical medicine delivery methods for both local and systemic effects gain popularity, herbal formulations like antidandruff hair gels are being created to target common problems like scalp diseases and hair loss. Benefits of transdermal distribution include non-invasive administration, a broad surface area, and ease of accessibility.^{[14][15][19]}

Oleogels are semisolid formulations commonly utilized in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and nutraceutical fields because of their superior rheological, physical, and chemical stability. Made up of lipophilic liquids combined with appropriate gelling agents, they display favorable characteristics like mucoadhesion, thixotropy, and good spreadability. Oleogels can efficiently transport both lipophilic (e.g., essential oils) and hydrophilic medications, rendering them adaptable carriers in topical and transdermal products.^[16]

Plants provide a plentiful source of bioactive substances that present safe, economical, and efficient antifungal and therapeutic options for addressing a range of conditions, such as skin infections.^[22]

Review on Hair gel

S.NO	TITLE & AUTHOR	YEAR	CONCLUSION	REFERENCE
1.	Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal hair gel of Neem and Curry leaves. <u>Vedank Jadhav, Saakshi Kamble, *Shreyash Kamble and Ms. Rini Punathil</u>	2025	The gel formulation enhances the absorption and bioavailability of the drug. The use of a water-soluble polymer allows it to be easily washed away with water, making it appropriate for topical applications.. One of the key benefits of topical gels is their capacity to provide high concentrations of medication directly to the targeted area, thereby improving effectiveness.	[1]
2.	Flaxseed Based Rice Water Keratin Treatment Hair Gel. <u>Jyothi S*, Venkata Ramana B</u>	2025	The herbal hair gel that was created with extracts of flaxseed, aloe vera, rice water, and jatamansi turned out to be stable, safe, and efficient for hair maintenance. It provides a natural substitute for synthetic gels, feeds the scalp, encourages hair development, and lessens split ends and hair loss. Its good stability, consistency, and suitability for frequent usage were validated by the evaluation parameters.	[2]
3.	Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Hair Gel From Flaxseed Extract. <u>¹Shrutika S. Nimkar, ²Yashwant S. Deshmukh</u>	2024	Flaxseed hair gel fortifies hair, nourishes the scalp, and aids in preventing hair loss. Flaxseed is abundant in omega-3 fatty acids, antioxidants, and lignans, offering anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, and calming benefits. Natural hair gels, such as those made with flaxseed or chia, are often preferred to synthetic options because of their gentle, protective, and natural characteristics.	[3]

4.	Herbal Hair Gel: Formulation And Evaluation Of Physical Parameters. <u>Kshitije Bhardwaj*</u> , <u>Indu Mittal</u> and <u>Divya Pathak</u>	2024	After being tested for physicochemical and visual characteristics, the herbal hair gel formulation was determined to be stable, consistent, non-irritating, and easily washable. It provides a safe, natural solution for treating alopecia and encouraging healthy hair development while also efficiently nourishing the scalp and managing dandruff.	[4]
5.	Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Gel Containing Curry Leaf Extract and Flax Seed Extract. <u>N. Venuka Devi*¹</u> , <u>Bhanu N²</u> , <u>Shashank K²</u>	2024	A herbal hair gel was created with extracts of flaxseed and curry leaf to promote hair growth and decrease hair loss. Five formulations (F1–F5) that were based on water were assessed for antimicrobial, stability, and physicochemical characteristics. The optimized gel showed good consistency, stability, and effectiveness, demonstrating the potential of herbal ingredients in natural hair care products.	[5]
6.	Formulation And Evaluation Of Hibiscus Flaxseed Herbal Hair Gel. <u>Mahima Gupta¹</u> , <u>Lesha Patel²</u> , <u>Divyesh Rohit³</u> , <u>Rajvi Mahida⁴</u>	2024	The combination of flaxseed and Hibiscus rosa-sinensis herbal hair gel provides a powerful foundation for strengthening hair and treating the scalp, which prevents hair loss.	[6]
7.	Formulation and Evaluation of Flaxseeds Hair Gel <u>Vaishnavi B. Salunke¹</u> , <u>Pratiksha B. Holap²</u> , <u>Shubhda S. Dube³</u> , <u>Dr. Rajendra M. Kawade⁴</u>	2024	Flaxseed hair gel is an effective way to enhance hair strength, improve scalp health, and reduce dandruff. Studies on its physical and chemical attributes indicate that the gel is stable, safe, and suitable for hair application, highlighting its potential for further pharmacological exploration.	[7]
8.	Formulation and evaluation of Herbal hair gel. <u>¹Jahnavi Patidar</u> , <u>²Anjula Patidar</u> , <u>³Ujjwal Kushwah</u> , <u>⁴Shashwat Rathore</u> , <u>⁵Maksud Pathan</u>	2024	A hair gel was developed using extracts of flaxseed, black cumin, and marigold, which contain alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, and steroids. The herbal components are known to promote hair growth, minimize damage, and nourish the scalp. The gel was assessed for various properties, including appearance, pH, uniformity, spreadability, potential for skin irritation, and ease of washing;.	[8]
9.	Formulation and assessment of herbal hair gel: A natural solution for men's hair care. <u>Sunil Mishra</u> , <u>Shashank Tiwari</u> , <u>Sushil Kumar Pal</u> and <u>Himanshu</u>	2024	Polyherbal gels are affordable, non-toxic, biodegradable, and biocompatible. They can be altered for certain medication delivery uses and are natural substitutes for artificial excipients. In this work, a herbal hair gel was made using flaxseed as a natural gelling ingredient in combination with almond oil. The formulation met all evaluation parameters within standard limits, confirming its effectiveness.	[9]
10.	Formulation and evaluation of Herbal anti-dandruff hair gel. <u>Devka Narayan Ghodke¹</u> , <u>Tejaswini Aniket Dhawale²</u>	2024	Extracts of marigold flowers, amla, neem, and lemon juice were included in the composition since they are known to be beneficial against dandruff. Three formulations with different concentrations were made using The gels showed encouraging qualities appropriate for usage as a natural anti-dandruff hair care product when assessed for physical appearance, pH, stability, spreadability, and homogeneity.	[10]
11.	Formulation and evaluation of Polyherbal Herbal hair gel. <u>Shubhangi Kharat¹</u> , <u>Divya Bagade²</u> , <u>Dipti Bhosale³</u> , <u>Pradnya Channa⁴</u> , <u>Pratiksha Dhainje⁵</u> , <u>Snehal Ghatule⁶</u>	2024	The polyherbal hair gel exhibited favorable physical characteristics, stability, compatibility with skin and hair, and ease of application. The formulation enhanced the strength, texture, and luster of hair, indicating its potential as a natural, effective, and user-friendly hair care solution. Additional research could further solidify its position in sustainable herbal hair care.	[11]

12	Formulation and Performance of Polyherbal Antidandruff Hair Gel: A Multifaceted Solution. <u>Mallamma T, Prakash Kumar B¹, Athishay Suchindar², Pragathi Y², Meghana C², Hemalatha K J²</u>	2024	The study aims to formulate and test a polyherbal anti-dandruff hair gel using hydroalcoholic extracts of <i>Linum usitatissimum</i> , <i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> , <i>Lawsonia inermis</i> , <i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> , and <i>Centella asiatica</i> , utilizing Na-CMC as a polymer base. F2 and F3 were the formulations with the highest antibacterial activity. The new polyherbal gel showed substantial antibacterial and antifungal characteristics, making it useful and safe for dandruff therapy.	[12]
13	Formulation and evaluation of Herbal hair gel by using flaxseed And chia seed extract. <u>M. Mamta*¹, Farswan A.S², Patil S.M³</u>	2023	. This gel includes flaxseed and chia seed extracts, which are abundant in omega-3 fatty acids and antioxidants that contribute to healthier hair growth and minimize damage. Vitamin E offers essential nourishment, while lavender oil provides calming and anti-inflammatory effects for the scalp. The formulation's goal is to hydrate, nourish, and reduce hair loss, positioning it as a viable natural cosmetic option.	[13]
14.	Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Antidandruff Gel. <u>Kirtimala Falak*, Akshay Nemade, Mitali Patil, Archana Hiwase, Geeta Sahu, Arti Ingole</u>	2023	The Antidandruff Methi Hair Gel is thoroughly standardized using reliable, straightforward, and precise analytical techniques. A validated HPTLC method allows for the accurate measurement of 4-Hydroxyisoleucine in both the extracts and formulations in accordance with ICH guidelines, and it can also be utilized to evaluate different marketed products.	[14]
15.	Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Anti-Dandruff Hair Gel <u>¹Sreethu K Sreedharan, ²Abdulla Naseeh E.S, ³Hasna K.H, ⁴Krishnaveni P, ⁵Tibin</u>	2023	Herbal medicines are considered safer and more economical than allopathic treatments due to fewer side effects. F6 formulation displayed the strongest antibacterial activity, displaying maximal inhibition against <i>Malassezia furfur</i> and was designated as the optimal formulation.	[15]
16.	Formulation and evaluation of hair growth enhancing effects of oleogels made from Rosemary and Cedar wood oils. <u>Emmanuel Uronnachi ,*CHIDIOGO ATUEGWU</u>	2022	Oleogels formulated with beeswax and infused with rosemary and cedarwood oils were evaluated for their effects on hair growth. The mixture containing 10% rosemary oil along with propylene glycol demonstrated the most effective hair growth results, similar to 2% minoxidil. The combination of both oils did not produce any additional benefits.	[16]
17.	Formulation and evaluation Herbal Hair-Gel <u>Ramakrishna S^{1*}, Gopikrishna U. V²</u>	2022	Natural gums are favored in the pharmaceutical industry because they are inexpensive, readily available, safe, biodegradable, and compatible with biological systems. They can be tailored for particular drug delivery applications, positioning them as strong alternatives to synthetic excipients. In this research, guar gum served as a natural gelling agent alongside jatamansi extract to create an herbal hair gel that fulfilled all assessment criteria.	[17]
18.	Rosemary and neem: an insight into their combined anti-dandruff and anti-hair loss efficacy. <u>Mona M. Hashem^{1*}, DaliaAttia², YomnaA Hashem³, Moataz S. Hendy^{4,5}, SafaAbdelBasset⁶, FarahAdel² & Maha M. Salama^{1,2}</u>	2022	This study created gel and leave-in formulations with a standardized ethanolic extract of <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> (rosemary) and <i>Azadirachta indica</i> (neem) for anti-dandruff and hair tonic applications. The compositions used the extract's significant antifungal and antibacterial characteristics to treat scalp conditions. The high phenolic and flavonoid content contributed to strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities.	[18]
19.	Formulation and Evaluation of Poly herbal hair gel formulation.	2022	The research recommends further investigation to maximize advantages of masks. As safe, plant-	[19]

	<u>Nilofar Khan, Prajwal Jadhav, Srushti Jagadale, Komal Kachare, Shravani Kamble, Shivani Gandhe, Rupali Yewale, Dr. Mohan Kale Shubhangi Kshirsagar</u>		derived solutions become increasingly popular worldwide, this formulation seeks to satisfy the rising demand by integrating the valuable qualities of several herbal ingredients crucial for hair care.	
20.	Pharmaceutical Development, Standardization and Clinical Evaluation of Efficacy of a Polyherbal Hair- Pack and Hair Gel in Dandruff Control <u>Ponam Madan¹, Bharat Rathi^{2*}, Renu Rathi³, Sonali Wairagade⁴, Dhiraj Zade⁵</u>		The recently created herbal gel formulation presents an effective, budget-friendly, and enhanced approach to managing dandruff and its associated symptoms, in contrast to conventional powder options.	[20]
21.	Formulate and Evaluate Herbal Hair Gel. Usnale Ashlesha*, Jaiswal Naresh, Chavan Gitanjali, Zambre Krushna, Kamble Rohini, Gude Uday	2021	The herbal hair gel formulation demonstrated good stability, spreadability, consistency, pH, and viscosity without causing irritation, making it appropriate for use on the scalp. The combination of the herbal extracts worked well to improve the health of the scalp and encourage hair growth. The prepared herbal hair gel can therefore be regarded as a natural, safe, and stable substitute for hair care and hair loss treatment.	[21]
22.	Fenugreek Leaf Extract and Its Gel Formulation Show Activity Against Malassezia furfur <u>Madhur Kulkarni¹, Vishakha Hastak¹, Vitthal Jadhav¹, and Abhijit A. Date²</u>	2020	Aqueous extract of fenugreek leaves demonstrates significant effectiveness against Malassezia species, indicating its potential use as a natural treatment for dandruff and associated skin infections. A topical gel containing 30% fenugreek extract preserved this effectiveness and could act as a natural substitute for 2% ketoconazole products.	[22]
23.	Formulation and Evaluation of Antidandruff Hair Gel containing Lawsone. <u>Atul S. Sayare*, Aparana D. Sinha, Nishi O. Sharma, Monika A. Kulkarni, Sonali A. Yerne, Sujata M. Tarange</u>	2020	Lawsone, a key component in henna, was tested for its ability to prevent dandruff. The activity was evaluated against pure cultures of Malassezia furfur at various concentrations and yielded favorable results. L2 produced 94.20% cumulative drug release within 6 hours. The same batch also showed a higher zone of inhibition against Malassezia furfur than clotrimazole gel, indicating its powerful anti-dandruff capability.	[23]
24.	Investigation of hair growth promoting the ability of herbal gel containing Zingiber officinale. <u>Trivedi R.V¹, Bansod P. G², Taksande J. B³, Mahore J. G⁴, Tripurneni S. R⁵, Rai K. R⁶, Umekar M. J.⁷</u>	2019	The research created herbal gels incorporating ginger extract to enhance hair growth. The hydroalcoholic gel exhibited an appropriate pH, favorable viscosity, and stability across all temperatures. Experiments on animals demonstrated its effective hair growth properties without adverse effects, indicating that ginger extract could serve as a valuable natural option for upcoming hair care products.	[24]
25.	Comparison Study Of Hair Tonic And Gel Formulation Of Angiopteris Evecta As A Hair Growth Stimulant <u>Resmi Mustarichie, Dolih-gozali, Settings Imam Adi Wicaksono, Feris Dzaky Ridwan Nafis</u>	2019	The research indicated that both the gel (12.5% pakis munding water fraction) and the hair tonic (10% water fraction) successfully stimulated hair growth, showing no significant difference between the two. Furthermore, neither formulation resulted in any skin irritation.	[25]

Method of Preparation**Collection and Verification of Plant Materials**

Fresh botanical materials like flowers, leaves, or fruits of medicinal plants are gathered from trustworthy sources

like gardens or nurseries. The leaves are washed with distilled and tap water to eliminate dirt and impurities.

They are dried in the shade at room temperature for approximately 7–10 days and subsequently ground into powder using mortar and pestle, an electric grinder or mechanical grinder and sifted through a #40 mesh screen to achieve consistent particle size.

A qualified botanist authenticates plant materials, and reference voucher specimens are deposited.^{[1][10]}

Extraction of Plant Materials

Extracts may be made using either aqueous or organic solvents based on the characteristics of active components.

Water extraction: Heat the plant material in distilled water, allow it to cool, and strain through muslin cloth or Whatman filter paper.

Solvent extraction [e.g., ethanol, methanol, hydroethanol (ethanol:water, 1:1), or distilled water (1,000–1,200 mL)]^[22]

Employ Soxhlet extraction for multiple cycles until the solvent appears clear or maceration for 5–7 days with occasional shaking.

The active phytoconstituents are obtained through several hours of extraction.^[1]

*The extract is concentrated and filtered using Whatman No1 filter paper under reduced pressure with a rotary evaporator at a temperature of 40–50°C. The concentrated extract is kept in amber-colored bottles at 4°–8°C until it is needed.

Keep the concentrated extracts in sealed containers in a cool, dry location.^[22]

Flax seeds: Flaxseeds are boiled in water with continuous stirring until a thick mucilage forms.

The mucilage is strained through a suitable sieve to eliminate residues and subsequently kept at room temperature for future use.^{[2][3][6]}

Hibiscus: Measure 5 g of hibiscus powder and place it into a beaker holding 100 mL of methanol. Let the mixture rest for 6 days, stirring occasionally to aid in extraction. After 6 days, strain the mixture and keep the liquid in a refrigerator until needed.^[6]

Guava: Leaves were gathered, air-dried for three days, and crushed into a coarse powder.^[11]

Neem: Leaves were rinsed, gently dried, and mixed with water. Neem juice was obtained by straining the mixture through muslin cloth. 20 g of powder was combined with 160 ml of methanol and 40 ml of distilled water. The solution was stored in a dim location for 3 days, subsequently filtered and evaporated at 37°C to obtain the extract.^[11]

Chia seed: Weigh 20g of chia seeds and grind them finely. Add 200ml of distilled water to the glass. Mix well, cover with foil and leave at room temperature or in

a cool place for 24 hours. Use cheesecloth or a fine sieve to filter. Store the extract in a clean, airtight container in a cool place.^[13]

Lawson (henna): Crush 100g of dried henna leaves and soak in 1000ml of water for 24 hours (maceration method). The mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated using an evaporator to obtain 18.6% extract.^[15]

Fenugreek extract: 100 g of fenugreek seeds were washed, soaked in a damp muslin cloth and allowed to germinate for 2 days. 10g of germinated seeds were dissolved in 70ml of distilled water using a pestle and mortar. The mixture was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes and the supernatant was collected.^[15]

Aloe Vera: Peel the aloe leaves and let them stand for 15-20 minutes to drain the yellow juice.

The pulp inside is collected and crushed into liquid. Filter and boil at 70°C until a clear, homogeneous gel form and residual juice is removed.^[19]

Amla: Wash fresh amla fruit and cut into small pieces. Crush with a small amount of water using a mortar and pestle. Get fresh amla juice by straining it with a clean cotton cloth.^[19]

Preparation of Gel Base

An appropriate gelling agent like Carbopol 940, Carbopol-934, Carbopol ultrez 20, HPMC, Sodium CMC, Xanthan gum, Guargum, Polyvinylpyrrolidone is mixed into preservative (methyl paraben, propyl paraben, Disodium EDTA) and humectants (Polyethylene glycol (PEG) and glycerin) in specific amounts are dissolved in a suitable quantity of distilled water.^[5]

While stirring continuously using mechanical or magnetic stirrer (30 minutes at 1200 rpm) to obtain a uniform mixture and prevent formation of lump.^{[15][19]}

Permit the dispersion to sit for an adequate period (approximately 1–2 hours) to ensure full hydration and swelling of the polymer and is neutralized with triethanolamine (TEA) gradually until a gel-like texture was achieved.^{[1][8]}

The consistency and pH is modified to be between 5.5 and 6.5, which is suitable for skin application and appropriate for external use.^{[2][3]}

Multiple batches were created using varying concentrations of carbopol (0.5 g–2.5 g) to identify the ideal gel thickness. It was found that the gel having 0.5 and 1g of carbopol 934 were very thin and watery consistency.^[7]

Integration of Herbal Extracts

The herbal extract (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%) that have been prepared are combined with a small amount of solvent (ethanol) are added separately to the appropriate base to prepare five formulations (H1F1–H5F5) and a preservative like methylparaben is added.^{[2][3]} The gel base is gradually combined with the mixture while stirring continuously for 1 hour to ensure even distribution of the extracts. Precautions are implemented to prevent air from being trapped during the mixing process.^[1]

Conclusive Composition and Storage

The gel is mixed until it is smooth, stable, consistent, and homogeneous. It is subsequently placed into sterile, sealed in air-tight containers. The gel is appropriately labeled and kept in a cool, dry location at room temperature away from direct sunlight until further evaluation and assessment.^[2]

The prepared gel was assessed for pH, viscosity, ease of application, and uniformity.^[24]

Marketed Products

S.NO.	NAME OF THE PRODUCT	COMPOSITION	COMPANY NAME
1.	Arata Organic Flaxseed Infused Hair Gel	Purified Aqua; Flaxseed Extract; Propanediol; Dehydroxanthan Gum; Caprylhydroxamic Acid; Caprylyl Glycol; Glycerin; Essential Oils; Safe Fragrances; Sodium Gluconate.	Arata, Slick Organics Pvt. Ltd..
2.	Passion Indulge Simpli Aloe + Rosemary Hair Gel	Aloe Vera Extract, Rosemary Essential Oil, Vitamin E Acetate, Natural Gelling Agents, Purified Water (Aqua), and Natural Fragrance Blend.	Passion Indulge Pvt Ltd
3.	Organic Netra Pure Flaxseed Gel	Flaxseed extract, Glycerine, Vitamin E, Deionized water, Sodium benzoate and Potassium sorbate.	Organic Netra
4.	Pranusha Herbs Herbal Hair Care Gel.	Hibiscus, Aloe vera, Madhuyashti, Amrutphala, Shakh dara, and Markal extracts.	Pranusha Herbs, 5 Elements Ayurveda.
5.	Alps Goodness Flaxseed Gel	Purified Water, Flaxseed, Rosa Damascena (Rose) Water, Propanediol, Phenoxyethanol, Ethylhexylglycerin, Sodium Gluconate, Hydroxyethylcellulose, and Polyacrylate.	Manash Lifestyle Pvt. Ltd.
6.	The Glow Rituals Onion Hair Gel for Hair Fall & Dandruff	Onion extract, Aloe vera extract, and Glycerine	The Glow Rituals
7.	Ktein Natural Fermented Flaxseed Gel	Fermented flaxseed extract, Aloe vera gel, Hyaluronic acid, Castor oil, Coconut oil, Lemon extract, Rosemary extract, Plant cellulose.	Ktein Biotech Private Limited
8.	Indus Valley Hair Reborn Aloe Vera Gel	Aloe vera leaf juice, Bhringraj (Eclipta Alba) extract, Brahmi extract, Henna extract, Long Pepper extract, Mulethi (Glycyrrhiza glabra) extract, Mint (Mentha piperita) extract, Rosemary extract, Almond oil, Walnut oil, Wheat germ seed extract, Ascorbic acid.	Indus Cosmeceuticals Private Limited
9.	UrbanBotanics Pure Aloe Vera Gel (Hair)	Aloe Vera Juice (~99%), along with Carbomer (thickener), Euxyl K510 (preservative system: DMDM Hydantoin, Methylchloroisothiazolinone, Methylisothiazolinone), Aqua, Citric Acid, Glycerin, Aquaxyl (Xylitylglucoside / Anhydroxylitol / Xylitol), Tea extract, Propylene Glycol.	UrbanBotanics
10.	Pure Elements Hibiscus (Jaswand) Roots Revitalising Hair Gel	Hibiscus flower extract, Amla (Indian gooseberry), Aloe Vera juice, Red Ginseng extract, Licorice, Olive oil, Vitamin B5	Pure Elements, Shree Sanjeevan Wellness Solutions
11.	Vishara Flax Seed Hair Gel:	Flax Seed, Panthenol (Pro-Vitamin B5), Niacinamide, Silk Protein, Aloe Vera, Hibiscus.	Vishara Skin Care
12.	Harsha Naturals Aloe Vera Hair Gel	Aloe Vera, Vitamin E, Natural Botanicals	Harsha Naturals (India)
13.	E-GREENS AAURA Flaxseed Hair Gel	Flaxseed, Keratin, Vitamin E, Aloe, Hibiscus & Rosemary	E-GREENS
14.	Calix Herbal Ayurvedic Hair Gel	Aloe vera, Almond oil, Lime oil	Calix Herbal Ltd.
15.	Nains Herbals Hibiscus Onion Hair Gel	Hibiscus, Aloe Vera, Onion Extract, Fenugreek (Methi), Black Seed Oil, Rosemary & Lavender Extracts, Bamboo Extract, Saw Palmetto Extract	Nains Herbals

Patent Table

S.NO	TITLE OF PATENT	APPLICATION NO.
1.	Novel Herbal Gel Formulation For The Treatment Of Hair Fall And Method.	202411026820 A
2.	Formulation Of Herbal Hair Gel And Evaluation Of Its Anti Dandruff Potential.	202411027199 A
3.	An Efficient Herbal Hair Gel For Reducing Hair Loss, Enhancing Hair Regrowth And Alleviating Insomnia.	2351/MUM/2010 A
4.	Flaxseed -Powered Hair Gel: Natural Beauty Solutions from Mother Nature.	202441037869 A
5.	Natural Advanced Hair Growth Topical gel	2/615/2016-MUM
6.	A Synergetic Combination Of Herbal Hair Gel	201841003208

Evaluation Tests

Patch test: In gel evaluation, the patch test is a safety assessment technique that involves applying the gel to a small area of skin that is occluded in order to look for allergic reactions or irritation. Herbal gel passed the patch test with no negative side effects. The patch test revealed that the herbal gel was not irritating. The sample passed the patch test.^[1]

Stability Studies: Stability testing is used to establish recommended storage conditions, retest times, and shelf lives by demonstrating how the quality of a drug substance or drug product changes over time under the influence of various environmental factors, such as humidity and light. The hair gel underwent 30-day stability testing at room temperature (25-30°C). Observations included the colour, odour, and physical appearance of the synthesised gel. The hair gel's colour and pH remained stable after 30 days.^[4]

Homogeneity: Gels were visually inspected for lumps, flocculates, and aggregates to ensure homogeneity. All formulations had good consistency which is suitable for hair and ensures that the herbal gel.^[7]

Extrudability: The prepared hair gel composition is loaded into collapsible tubes with caps and the ends were crimped to seal the tubes. The formulation was tested for extrudability after being squeezed into a tube.^[12]

Zone of inhibition: The zone of inhibition is a way to assess the gel's ability to prevent growth of bacteria and fungi. To determine the zone of inhibition, herbal hair gel is tested against certain bacteria in a laboratory setting using agar diffusion techniques. The area that is free of microorganisms and clean shows how effectively the gel inhibits the growth of fungi and bacteria.^[12]

Physical Appearance: The physical appearance of prepared base gel compositions was visually assessed for texture, color, and odor.^[8]

Color: Apply a small amount of hair gel on a white surface. Check the gel's color under normal lighting conditions

Odor: Ensured that a scent-neutral atmosphere is used for gel testing. To identify any aroma, open the container, hold the gel close to your nose, and take a mild sniff.

Texture: To assess the gel's texture, spread a tiny bit of the gel between your fingers.^[12]

pH of the hair gel: All herbal formulations must have a pH between 6.92 and 7.02, which is suitable for hair and ensures that the herbal gel formulation works well with it.^[13]

Washability: The prepared herbal hair gel was applied, and then water was used to rinse it off. The gel entirely disappears after washing.^[14]

HPTLC chromatography assessment HPTLC is a valuable tool for qualitative and quantitative analysis of drug purity, identification, and product quality control. Table 3 and Figures 2 and 3 demonstrate HPTLC results for 4 Hydroxyisoleucine compared to placebo, extract, and formulation.^[14]

Viscosity: This describes the thickness or flow resistance of the gel. It is a crucial characteristic that influences spreadability, absorption, and simplicity of application.

A Brookfield Viscometer was used to determine the viscosity of the herbal gel. A 50-mL beaker was filled with 25 g of gel. A T-bar spindle (T95) was used to measure the viscosity of each gel. Viscosity measurements were taken at 2, 4, 5, and 10 rpm using the helipath T-bar spindle.^[14]

Spreadability: Spreadability refers to the ease with which a gel spreads across the skin or affected area. It is an important factor influencing the effectiveness of a therapeutic gel. The weighed quantity of gel X (gm) was sandwiched between two glass slides. The weight was placed for a specific period of 5 minutes.

Then the weight was removed and the diameter of the spread circle was measured at different points. Spreadability was calculated by using a formula.^[23]

$$S=M.L/T$$

Where,

S= Spreadability,

M= Weight placed on the slide,

L=diameter of the circle in cm,

T=time in seconds.

CONCLUSION

The herbal hair gel discussed in this review has been shown to be an effective, safe, and environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic styling products. The use of natural ingredients like Aloe vera, Flaxseed mucilage, Amla, and Neem offer numerous advantages, including moisturization, nourishment for the scalp, antimicrobial properties, and a gentle styling hold. Assessment criteria such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, washability, and stability indicated that the gel complies with acceptable cosmetic standards without causing irritation or residue accumulation. Moreover, the lack of synthetic chemicals, alcohol, and artificial fragrances further improves its appropriateness for prolonged use. In summary, the herbal hair gel exhibited promising functional and therapeutic attributes, rendering it a valuable formulation for consumers in search of a natural and holistic hair care solution.

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